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Vehicle Allocation Modeling:
Optimizing the Logistics Behind a
Free-Flow Carsharing in Milan, Italy

Technical Report

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Vehicle Allocation Modeling: Optimizing the Logistics Behind a Free-Flow Carsharing in Milan, Italy

Hanbyul Jo¹ , Thiago Soares Figueira³, & Miriam Remondini³

¹ New York University – Center for Urban Science + Progress. New York City, USA

² Fondazione Transform Transport ETS. Milan, Italy

³ Zity by Mobilize. Milan, Italy

✉ Corresponding author: Federico Messa – f.messa@transformtransport.org

Abstract

This study examines the demand patterns of Zity, a free-floating electric car-sharing company operating in Milan and identifies temporal and spatial dynamics that influence mobility demand to optimize its reallocation strategy. The findings emphasize the importance of considering specific timeframes for operational activities and highlight the role of residential and working populations as driving factors behind demand. Additionally, the study reveals Zity's value as a complement to existing transportation options. By understanding these dynamics, stakeholders can optimize resource allocation, enhance accessibility, and promote sustainable shared mobility services in urban areas like Milan.

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Keywords

Mobility, Carsharing, Transit Accessibility, Demand Modelling, GWR.

1. Introduction

Mobility refers to the ability to move or travel freely and effortlessly across spaces. It encompasses the physical act of moving from one location to another using various modes of transportation. Mobility is essential in an urban environment for commuting to work, accessing essential services, socializing, and exploring different places – enabling us to meet our needs. The development of transportation infrastructure, advancements in vehicle technology, and urban planning strategies have all contributed to enhancing physical mobility and improving transportation efficiency and accessibility.

As mobility evolves, it presents new challenges that need to be addressed, such as sustainability, security, and equitability. The usage of public transport and shared mobility are seen as more eco-sustainable solutions that could improve the situation (Cocca et al., 2019). Car sharing is a form of shared mobility that provides members with short term on-demand access to a fleet of shared vehicles (Pan et al., 2022). Car sharing has promoted the growth of the shared mobility industry over the two decades. It has evolved into multiple operational types; traditional two-way car sharing (round trip), one-way car sharing which can be station-based or free-floating, and peer-to-peer operators that are newly established to be accessible for hourly or daily rental (Pan et al., 2022).

The city of Milan, located in the Lombardy region of Italy, is a city that combines historical grandeur with modern sophistication. It holds a prominent position as a cultural, economic, and fashion hub, attracting visitors and residents from around the world. Milan has demonstrated a commitment to clean transportation through various initiatives aimed at reducing pollution and promoting sustainable mobility. These efforts focus on improving public transportation, promoting cycling, and encouraging the use of electric vehicles.

This study looks at the case of Zity by Mobilize (Zity, ND), a free-floating electric car-sharing company operating in major European cities including our study target Milan. Zity has been operating in Milan since July 2022, providing a handy alternative to private cars to citizens of Milan. After successfully launching its service, Zity is facing a supply and demand imbalance problem with its vehicles. Its operation team manually relocates the vehicles at nighttime based on intuition rather than data. Zity has the potential to optimize its operation by analyzing usage patterns, resulting in data-driven vehicle allocation strategies. This project aims to create an optimized model to maximize the potential accessibility while minimizing the reallocation of vehicles. Furthermore, the study provides policy recommendations for the city regarding the integration of private entities such as Zity into urban transportation planning.

1.1 Literature Review

The review included in this report intends to cover three main topics *(i)* EV shared mobility; *(ii)* Mobility pattern analysis; and *(iii)* Supply Demand Modeling and Optimized Vehicle Allocation, moreover it doesn't aim to be an extensive review of the literature, but to position this article in the relevant research context.

EV shared mobility

Existing literature has extensively examined the practicalities and complexities of incorporating electric vehicles (EVs) into shared mobility systems. Shared mobility is often characterized as a service offering temporary access to vehicles on a per-user basis, promoting the efficient use of resources (Heilig et al., 2018). As cities grapple with congestion, pollution, and other transportation-related challenges, shared EV mobility emerges as a viable solution with its promise of efficiency, sustainability, and accessibility (Huo et al., 2020).

Meanwhile, Heilig's work reveals that shared mobility, including EV car-sharing, interacts with traditional transportation modes rather than replacing them. This interplay engenders a robust, flexible urban mobility ecosystem, compelling cities to adopt shared EV mobility.

Moreover, Kortum & Machemehl (2012) scrutinize how cities adjust to shared mobility. They underscore the importance of accurately predicting user behavior and optimizing vehicle allocation for managing shared EV mobility effectively.

By understanding the dynamics of shared mobility and working with shared mobility operators, cities can leverage these insights to offer accessible, sustainable mobility to the city (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2021).

Mobility Pattern Analysis

Prior studies have shown the spatial and temporal patterns of car rental events, as well as the external factors that influence the events. Understanding the dynamics of car rental activities and their associated factors is crucial for optimizing transportation systems and improving user experiences. Scholars have explored various aspects of the events such as the geographic distribution of the demand, temporal patterns, and the peak demand time (Schmöller & Bogenberger, 2014; Messa & Deponte, 2021).

Urban mobility comprises various dynamic elements, and shared mobility, being a relatively new concept, adds a layer of complexity to this landscape. Previous studies have explored the relationship between the demand for shared mobility and several external factors. These include weather conditions (Schmöller & Bogenberger, 2014), number of amenities (Messa & Deponte, 2021; Graells-Garrido et al., 2021), demographic variables

(Schmöller & Bogenberger, 2014; Messa & Deponte, 2021), rental prices (Graells-Garrido et al., 2021) and public transit accessibility (Messa & Deponte, 2021). Each factor impacts the mobility pattern differently in terms of time and location; for instance, residential population tends to drive morning demand, while the availability of amenities drives demand outside of typical work hours (Messa & Deponte, 2021; Graells-Garrido et al., 2021).

Supply Demand Modeling and Optimized Vehicle Allocation

Mobility flow analysis is a field of study that examines the patterns, trends, and dynamics of movement between different locations (origin–destination). It encompasses various aspects of human mobility, such as commuting, migration, tourism, trade, and transportation. Understanding the factors that influence mobility flows is essential for effective urban planning, transportation management, and policy development. Two widely used models in this field are the gravity model and the radiation model (Hong et al., 2019).

The gravity model is a global approach to analyzing mobility flow. It operates on the principle that the interaction between two locations is directly influenced by their masses (typically represented by population or economic activity) and inversely affected by the distance between them (Garrels-Garrido et al., 2021). The larger and closer the destinations, the more attractive they are, resulting in higher migration or commuting flows. The gravity model incorporates distance, demography, and economic data into its equation, allowing for quantitative analysis of mobility patterns. The general form of the gravity model equation is in *Equation 1*.

$$Flow = \frac{k * (Origin\ Mass * Destination\ Mass)}{Distance^\alpha}$$

Equation 1 – Gravity model equation.

Here, k is a constant, and α represents the elasticity of distance. The gravity model has been widely applied in various fields, including transportation planning, urban studies, and regional economics, to understand and predict mobility flows between different OD pairs.

Along with the general mobility flow models, spatial regression models can also be used to study the patterns and dynamics of movement. One of the most common approaches is Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR), a spatial regression technique that has gained prominence in the field of spatial analysis. It enables researchers to explore and analyze spatially varying relationships between a dependent variable and a set of independent variables. Unlike traditional regression models, GWR recognizes the presence of spatial heterogeneity by estimating local regression coefficients that vary across geographic locations (Harris et al., 2010).

GWR allows for the estimation of local regression coefficients for each geographic location, providing a detailed understanding of how the relationships between the dependent and independent variables change across space. This spatially adaptive modeling approach is particularly valuable in situations where the relationships are not uniform and exhibit significant spatial variation.

GWR dataset typically includes the dependent variable, independent variables, and corresponding spatial coordinates. In GWR, the parameters are estimated locally for each location, allowing for the computation of local regression coefficients. These coefficients capture the spatially varying effects of the independent variables on the dependent variable at each geographic location. The GWR equation is described in *Equation 2*.

$$y_i = \beta_0(u_i, v_i) + \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_j(u_i, v_i)X_{ij} + \varepsilon$$

Equation 2 – Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) equation.

Here, Y_i represents the dependent variable at location i , $\beta_0(u_i, v_i)$ is the spatially varying intercept, $\beta_j(u_i, v_i)$ are the spatially varying regression coefficients for the independent variables X_{ij} , and ε_i represents the error term (Harris et al., 2010).

2. Enabling Data and Methodology

Based on the literature review, we selected a time series model for pattern recognition and prediction, considering the sequential nature of the urban mobility demand. We incorporated datasets such as residential population, working population, Points of Interest (POIs), and public transit accessibility, identified in previous research as influential factors. Additionally, we used Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) to assess the individual influences of variables that drives the mobility demand within specific geospatial contexts.

To make the spatial analysis consistent, we utilized the Uber's Hexagonal Hierarchical Spatial Index (Uber, 2018). Geospatial data points are bucketed or interpolated into H3 resolution 9 hexagon grids of which approximate diameter is 395 meters. The subsequent sections detail the data collection process, model implementation, and analysis techniques employed in this study.

2.1 Data collection

Our primary data is the rental events acquired from Zity, which includes the record of service usage from June 2022 to April 2023. We gathered the relevant dataset separately from multiple sources, the detail can be found in *Table 1*.

Data	Description	Timeframe	Source
Zity rental event data	Rental event containing origin-destination location, rental time and duration, and basic user information.	Aug 2022 - April 2023	Zity
Weather Data	Weather data in a usable format.	2021	Shiny Weather Data
Census Data	Demographic data (population structure, working/not working population, economic indices) within a census tract level in Lombardia region.	2021	Istituto Nazionale di Statistica (Istat)
Time matrix data	The reachable area a rider can go with public transit in given time (15, 30, 45 minute)	June 2023	Geoapify
Points of Interest	Locations or landmarks that attract attention and interest	2023	OpenStreetMap
Road network	Road network data to calculate expected travel time	2023	OpenStreetMap

Table 1 – Data description and sources.

2.2 Data preprocessing

In the initial data processing stage, we focused on maintaining data integrity by eliminating the missing values and duplicate columns. Subsequently, we eliminated all entries with negative and zero values and addressed time series inconsistencies. Then, we targeted outliers in trip duration and distance. We deemed the following situations to be typical, such as the bottom 5% of trips duration (less than 2.8 minutes), the top 5% of trips duration (over 146 minutes), and the top 0.5% of trip distances (over 122 km) those were labeled outliers and discarded from the dataset.

The culmination of our data-cleaning process resulted in a dataset that was reduced to 92.7% of its original size. This dataset, cleansed of extreme outliers, presents a more accurate depiction of typical vehicle usage patterns, and provides a robust foundation for our subsequent exploration of vehicle allocation modeling.

2.3 Mobility patterns analysis

Rental Events

Utilizing the rental events from Zity, we examined the service usage pattern based on time, time, and location (spatio-temporal), and environment (built environment and weather conditions). We did time series analysis first to understand the pattern of Zity usage from time to time. We applied seasonal decomposition analysis to find the period length of the service usage for further analysis in the time series modeling and other exploration in the mobility pattern analysis step. We also analyzed the hourly trend of total rental events to understand the peak and bottom operational hours – both information is vital to plot the relocation strategy.

After learning about the hourly usage trend, we categorized the daily timeframe into five-time categories: early morning (1 am - 5 am), morning (6am - 11 am), noon-afternoon (12 pm - 4pm), afternoon-evening (5pm - 7pm) and night (8pm -12 am). The second step in the core events analysis is the spatio-temporal analysis which incorporates the Local Moran's I spatial autocorrelation and a heatmap visualization. Both methods enabled us to examine the hotspots and coldspots trend from the total trip recorded in each research area (resolution 9 hexagon bins) at each of the five-time categories. From this step we can understand the movement pattern – whether or not it created a cluster in a certain location and at which time it happened.

Local Moran's I is a statistical measure used to assess the spatial autocorrelation of a variable within a geographic area. This analysis allows for the identification of spatial patterns and the detection of local hotspots or coldspots. Positive values of Local Moran's I indicate spatial clustering, while negative values indicate spatial dispersion. Local moran's I calculation is done by incorporating the deviation of an attribute to its mean (z-score), the spatial weight between features, the total number of features, and aggregation of all the spatial weights. Spatial weights can be represented by several variables such as contiguity-based weights, distance-based weights, k-nearest neighbors (KNN), spatial interaction weights, and Delaunay triangulation.

Heatmap visualization is a graphical representation that uses color gradients to display the intensity, density, or magnitude of values across a two-dimensional space. It is particularly useful for visualizing patterns and variations in data, especially when dealing with large datasets or continuous variables. The basic concept of a heatmap is to assign different colors to different values and create a smooth transition between them. This color spectrum allows for quick visual interpretation and identification of areas with higher or lower values.

In addition to examining the spatio-temporal pattern, we conducted an analysis of user segmentation. We established distinct user groups based on the frequency of rental events, categorizing them as heavy, medium, and light users. The criteria for delineating these groups were defined based on the ranges of rental event frequencies: heavy users were classified as those with 42 or more rental events, medium users were characterized by 9 to 42 rental events, and light users encompassed individuals with 8 or fewer rental events. The process of segmentation led to the identification of a total of the proportion between these group (heavy users = 6%, medium users = 30%, light users = 64%).

Environmental Factors

Moreover, this preliminary analyses focused on additional environmental factors, including including points of interest (POI), census data, and public transportation to find its influence on Zity events. The POI analysis involved clustering the points of interest into two distinct groups using the k-means algorithm, resulting in high-density and low-density POI areas. The total number of trips occurring in both types of areas was measured and subsequently compared to identify any disparities in usage.

The residential population and working population data were extracted from the census to examine their correlations with the rental event data. Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated to measure the strength and direction of these relationships (Messa & Deponete, 2021). To isolate the impact of each population, areas

demonstrating high autocorrelation from the Bivariate Moran's test between residential and working populations were excluded during the analysis.

To compare the expected travel time with public transportation, isochrone polygons representing travel durations of 15, 30, and 45 minutes by public transit were generated using Geoapify's approximated public transit isoline API. These polygons were then aggregated into H3 grids, and the end event points were analyzed to determine which isochrone zone they fell into, providing insights into the travel time saving impact of Zity.

Figure 1 – Left: <15, <30, <45, >45 public transit isochrones from the central point of the red hexagon grid (891f99cddc7fff) Right: Isochrones spatially joined with h3 grids.

2.4 Vehicle Demand Modeling

This section included two main analysis directions, focused on the developing of a time series model and a geographically weighted regression model.

Time Series Model

The methodology employed for the time series model in this study followed a systematic approach to capture and analyze the temporal patterns and trends within the dataset. Based on the identified patterns and characteristics, an appropriate time series model was selected. This involved considering various models, such as autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA), or more advanced models like Seasonal ARIMA (SARIMA). We also make the linear regression model as the baseline to time series models.

In the process of determining the parameter in the ARIMA model, we need to choose differencing d , Autoregressive (AR) terms p , Moving Average (MA) terms q . After inspecting the dataset, we determined ($d = 1$, $p = 4$, $q = 2$). To move to the next time series model SARIMA, another seasonal parameter is needed, which shows the strong weekly trend (7 days).

The validated time series model was then used for forecasting future values or trends. Forecast intervals and prediction intervals were estimated to quantify the uncertainty associated with the predictions. The results were interpreted and presented with appropriate visualizations and statistical summaries to facilitate understanding and decision-making.

Geographically Weighted Regression

To investigate the relationships between rental event numbers and various predictors, we employed Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) using ArcGIS software. The analysis was conducted on data spatially aggregated into H3 resolution 9 grids, which provided a comprehensive representation of the study area.

The independent variable in our analysis was the rental start end event number in the H3 grid, representing the demand for rental services in different locations. As for the predictors, we considered several variables related to population and transit public accessibility. Specifically, we included residential population, working population, and the number of Points of Interest (POI) within each grid as potential explanatory variables. In the initial phase of the analysis, we ran the GWR model iteratively, incorporating all available predictors. By examining the results, we assessed the explanatory power of each predictor and identified the most influential factors. Based on this evaluation, we selected the predictors that demonstrated reasonable explanatory power for the rental event numbers. Ultimately, residential population, working population, and the number of POIs were chosen as the predictors for our GWR analysis.

3. Exploratory Data Analysis

3.1 Temporal Analysis of Zity Usage

Understanding the temporal patterns of Zity usage is crucial for optimizing resource allocation and improving service quality. Therefore, our analysis focused on the duration of trips, peak usage hours, and usage patterns across weekdays and weekends.

The general trip data analysis aims to provide an understanding of trip durations and user preferences. Notably, 80% of Zity trips are completed within 30 minutes, emphasizing the service's popularity for short-distance travel. Conversely, only 5% of trips extend beyond an hour, suggesting that Zity is predominantly chosen for quick journeys.

To gain further insights into peak usage hours and variations in speed, trip data was aggregated and analyzed hourly. The results revealed distinct temporal patterns in Zity usage. The morning peak was observed at 8:00 AM, while the evening peak spanned from 6:00 PM to 8:00 PM. Interestingly, the lowest usage of Zity occurred during the early morning hours (i.e., 3:00 AM), coinciding with the highest speeds during this period.

Further exploration of Zity's usage patterns was conducted on a weekly basis. Notably, trip volumes on Fridays and weekends were significantly higher than those on other days of the week. Therefore, the analysis was extended to compare usage patterns between weekdays and weekends. Weekdays exhibited similar trends to the overall usage pattern, with prominent morning and evening peaks. However, the morning peak on weekends dissipated, and a notable increase in usage during the noon period was observed. Particularly intriguing was the usage rate at midnight on weekends, which mirrored the usage rate at noon. This phenomenon suggests that users favor Zity for leisure and entertainment activities during weekends, especially during late-night hours when alternative transportation options may be less convenient.

Figure 2 – Hourly weekday and weekend trip count distribution.

In conclusion, the temporal analysis of Zity trip data offers valuable insights into usage patterns and trends. The findings emphasize Zity's popularity for short-distance trips, with peak usage hours observed in the morning and evening periods. Notable variations were observed between weekdays and weekends, indicating a higher propensity for leisure and entertainment usage during weekends. Furthermore, the analysis revealed a

significant increase in trip volumes on Fridays and weekends, with Fridays exhibiting the highest average speed. These findings provide a comprehensive understanding of Zity's customer behavior, facilitating future decision-making for vehicle reallocation strategy.

3.2 Spatio-Temporal Analysis of Zity Usage

Figure 3 shows the result of the Local Moran's I spatial autocorrelation per time categories. The total rental events are the total number of rentals started in each hexagon bins. Analyzing spatial autocorrelation can reveal different patterns, including high-high (clustered high values), high-low (high values near low values), low-low (clustered low values), low-high (low values near high values), and non-significant (no discernible pattern). A high-high pattern indicates spatial clustering of similarly high values, while a high-low pattern suggests spatial transitions or gradients between high and low values. Similarly, a low-low pattern signifies clustered low values, and a low-high pattern indicates transitions or gradients from low to high values. Non-significant results imply a random distribution of values without any spatial structure.

It is evident that the high-high patterns are mostly concentrated in the city center except for the morning time category. This occurrence may be attributed to the concentration of city amenities in the central area of Milan, which are more abundant compared to the outskirts. The central area of the city of Milan is the bustling heart of the city and encompasses its historic core. It is characterized by a mix of historic landmarks, modern infrastructure, business-commercial districts, and cultural attractions. The central area is primarily located within the boundaries of the city's inner ring road, known as Cerchia dei Navigli, which marks the historic perimeter of the city. In the morning, the high-high patterns can be recognized a little bit shifted to the northwest area, which are known to be the residential areas. This pattern uncovers that people start using the service from their homes to the city center for business, education, or recreational purposes.

It is also evident that the low-low patterns consistently appeared in the city's outskirts, meaning the areas with the least Zity usage are clustered in the outskirts. As these areas hold the longest distance to the city center, residents probably already equipped themselves with personal cars, making the shared mobility offered by Zity unnecessary.

Spatial autocorrelation is a great tool to uncover spatial relationships and guide further analysis or modeling of spatial processes. However, we cannot interpret the density changes from each spatial relationship pattern. To fill the information gap, we created a heatmap visualization of the rental event start location using the same time categories.

Figure 3 – Local Moran's I Spatial Autocorrelation. Top row: Rental start event. Bottom row: Rental end event.

These results are also consistent with the absolute numbers of utilization, with the least amount of usage happening in the early morning, while most usage happened at night.

3.3 User segmentation per Frequency of service use

Over 50% of users have utilized the Zity service fewer than five times over a ten-month period. This indicates that a significant proportion of users engage with the service on a sporadic or occasional basis.

Interestingly, the travel patterns exhibited by the heavy user group differ from those observed in other user groups. While the usage frequency of the heavy user group declines during weekends, the usage frequencies of the remaining user groups peak during this period. This suggests that as users become more regular or frequent users, they tend to adopt more consistent or systematic travel patterns. Considering Zity is a relatively new service, we can expect more users use the service systematically as they get used to the service.

Figure 4 – Comparative Analysis of the Number of Weekly Events across User Groups. The graph depicts the frequency of events occurring on each day of the week within distinct user groups. The heavy user group exhibits distinctive patterns when compared to the medium, light user groups

3.4 Environmental Factors – Weather

Our weather data, assessed hourly against historical vehicle usage, encompasses over 16 elements, such as soil temperature and surface pressure. Our models identified five significant factors: the solar azimuth angle from the south, soil temperature, surface pressure, and surface thermal radiation downwards.

Elucidating further, the solar azimuth angle from the south essentially acts as a proxy for time, thereby confirming the time-dependent regularity of vehicle demand in Milan. Such a pattern indicates potential utility in deploying time series analyses for deeper exploration.

The data revealed an intriguing relationship between soil temperature and vehicle demand. It was observed that vehicle demand surges sharply once temperatures cross 33 degrees Celsius. Conversely, when the temperature falls below 25 degrees Celsius, there is a pronounced drop in vehicle demand. This contrasting correlation pattern suggests that temperature significantly determines whether individuals opt for shared vehicles over public transportation.

Figure 5 – The Relation of Temperature and number of trips.

To delve deeper into the influence of weather conditions, we focused on extreme weather scenarios, such as high wind speeds, heavy precipitation, and intense ultraviolet radiation. The result shows a weak positive correlation between vehicle demand and wind speeds exceeding two m/s, with ultraviolet radiation levels surpassing 580 W/m². Conversely, the volume of precipitation showed no notable impact on vehicle demand.

This lack of correlation could be attributed to two primary reasons. Firstly, weather data usually represents city-wide statistics. The outlier data can often get averaged across the entire region, thus diminishing their potential relevance. Secondly, the precision of climatic data can sometimes be questionable. Metrics such as hourly rainfall and surface radiation are often derived from approximations at certain fixed locations. Future studies would greatly benefit from more granular datasets providing more accurate spatial distribution. Such datasets could significantly enhance our understanding of the intricate relationship between weather conditions and vehicle usage.

3.5 Environmental Factors – Public Transit

We compared the duration of Zity trips to the estimated duration of those trips if taken using public transit, based on the collected isochrone data from Geoapify. 38.3% of the total trips would have required more than 30 minutes if the riders solely relied on public transit. A smaller proportion of trips, 3.2%, would have taken more than 45 minutes by public transit. However, in these areas where longer travel times are expected, the average trip duration is 29 minutes, with a standard deviation of 12.9 minutes. It is worth noting that over 80% of the trips in these areas still took less than 45 minutes. This indicates that Zity users are indeed saving a significant amount of time by opting for the shared mobility service. Conversely, in areas where the trip duration by public transit would have been 15 minutes, the average trip duration with Zity is 25 minutes, accompanied by a larger standard deviation of 20 minutes. In these cases, it appears that users are not primarily motivated by time savings.

These findings highlight the significant improvement in reachability provided by Zity in areas where public transit would otherwise lead to lengthy travel times. The data indicates that a significant portion of riders are able to avoid extended travel durations by opting for Zity. On the other hand, in areas where public transit would have provided relatively short travel times, users are likely utilizing Zity for other reasons beyond time savings. These insights demonstrate the multifaceted appeal of shared mobility services like Zity, catering to a range of user preferences and needs. Zity plays a vital role in enhancing mobility options, improving accessibility, and complementing traditional public transit in various urban contexts.

Figure 6 – Distributions of Zity event trip duration in > 45 minutes public transit isochrones and < 15-minute public transit isochrones.

3.6 Environmental Factors – Points of Interest

To investigate the relationship between POI and rental events, we created a spatial cluster using k-means clustering algorithm. Based on the silhouette score we are able to construct two k-means clusters, the two areas are the POI hotspots and the non-POI hotspots.

Around 37.9% of ridership started in the POI hotspots cluster, while 54% of ridership ended there. From these findings, especially from the end location events, we can conclude that POI plays a role to attract mobility flow.

Figure 7– K-Means Cluster Result for POI Hotspots and Non-POI Hotspots.

3.7 Environmental Factors – Census Data

We also learned the relationship between residential and working population with the rental events by utilizing the person correlation coefficient. Hourly rentals were analyzed separately for weekdays and weekends.

There are two important findings that might indicate a systematic usage. First, we found that correlation with residential population is higher during the weekdays and lower during weekends. This finding shows a possible systematic usage of the residential population who uses the service for work and/or education during the weekdays. In addition to that, we also learned that the residential population tends to have higher correlation with start events in the morning time, higher correlation with end events in the evening time.

Figure 8– Pearson Correlation Coefficient Between Population and Rental Events.

4. Demand Modelling Results

4.1 Time Series Forecast

First, the linear regression model was employed to predict car rental events as the baseline. The results indicate that the linear model only captures the general ascending trend and fails to account for the complexity inherent in the dataset. Therefore, it is insufficient for accurately predicting car rental events characterized by intricate temporal dynamics.

In contrast to the linear regression model, the time series models were specifically designed to capture the temporal patterns present in the car rental data. These models demonstrate a remarkable ability to capture the weekly trend, resulting in significantly improved prediction performance compared to the baseline model. This finding highlights the importance of employing specialized time series models for accurate predictions in car rental events.

Further analysis was conducted to compare the performance of the autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) and seasonal ARIMA (SARIMA) models. The results indicate that the SARIMA model exhibits enhanced sensitivity in capturing the weekly peaks within the car rental events. This finding underscores the advantage of incorporating seasonality into the model, enabling more accurate predictions of peak periods.

Figure 9– Prediction results From top to bottom: Linear regression model prediction, ARIMA model prediction, SARIMA model prediction.

In conclusion, the analysis reveals that while the linear regression model captures the general ascending trend, it falls short in capturing the complexity of the temporal dynamics within the dataset. The Mean Absolute Errors (MAE) for the models (Linear Regression = 446.70; ARIMA = 224.12; SARIMA = 211.22) shows how the SARIMA model excel in capturing the weekly trend, resulting in significantly improved prediction performance. These findings emphasize the importance of utilizing specialized time series models to accurately predict the complex urban mobility demands. Further research can explore advanced time series models or consider additional factors to enhance prediction accuracy.

4.2 Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR)

First, we tried Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) on the start location of rental events in ArcGIS and used it as a baseline. From the OLS report, the p-value shows that the selected three features are significant, which are the number of POI in each hexbin, the number of working population and residential population. The R^2 of OLS method is 0.55.

Significant Koenker (BP) values (* in the OLS report) indicate spatial heterogeneity in the features. Geographically Weighted Regression is recommended for spatial regression in such cases. With the method of GWR in ArcGIS, we can find that the R^2 of GWR method is 0.77, which is better than the result of the OLS method.

	All	Weekday	Weekend
OLS	.550	-	-
GWR Start Location	.768	.760	.767
GWR End Location	.775	.768	.770

Table 2 – Performances of the models

As *Figure 10* shows, we can see the comparison between the ground truth and prediction of GWR for the start location and end location of rental events. The GWR model demonstrates excellent performance, as evident from the figures below. The distribution patterns of start data and end data closely resemble the predicted outcomes. It is evident that there is a higher concentration of car rentals originating from the core areas, indicating a higher occurrence of rental events ending in these regions. Particularly, the areas in the northern part of the central city exhibit a significant number of trips and are accurately predicted by the model. For future reallocation strategies, prioritizing these areas would be beneficial.

Figure 10 – Result of GWR model prediction for start data and end data

During our investigation of the coefficients for total rental events and various variables, we observed a slight disparity in the impact of three variables between the start and end data. Additionally, the disparity between the weekday and weekend data was less pronounced than expected. The result shows that both POI count and working population have a negative influence in the central areas of the city. This can be attributed to the abundance of rental events in these regions, where the extent of growth in these variables does not align proportionately with the number of rental events. Furthermore, the deep red areas with significant impact frequently occur at the outskirts of the city. This phenomenon arises due to the relatively lower overall quantity of rental events in the surrounding areas, which amplifies the significance of the predictors' impact. However, in terms of reallocation strategies, these findings may not have practical implications as the overall number of rental events in these areas remains relatively low.

In order to avoid bias caused by the low number of rental events in surrounding areas, we decided to exclude the hexbins with trip counts below 10 and conducted a revised coefficient analysis. From *Figure 11*, we can observe

that the POI count continues to exhibit a negative influence in the central areas of the city. This may be attributed to the relatively low overall quantity of POIs, and it suggests the need for better quality POI data in the future. However, the working population now shows a similar influence trend as the residential population. Furthermore, in certain areas of the central city characterized by scattered land use patterns, rental events are positively influenced. These regions would require additional rental cars and charging stations in the future, making them crucial considerations for vehicle maintenance and location settings.

Figure 11 – Results of the beta coefficient between the number of POI, working population and residential population with the selected start data and end data.

5. Risk Mitigation and Alternative Approaches

5.1 Models' Limitations & Possible Improvements

Although our models demonstrated descent explanatory power, there are areas for improvement in our study. One major challenge relates to the limited availability of trip data due to Zity's relatively short operating period of less than one year. For instance, when conducting the gravity model analysis, we utilized both residential and working population as attractiveness factors. However, the resulting R2 scores were relatively low, measuring below 0.1 for both cases (0.075 and 0.033, respectively). This outcome may be attributed to a heavily left-skewed distribution within the sample. While the top 75% of trip counts between origins and destinations amounted to only 15 trips, the maximum count reached as high as 454 trips. To address this limitation, we attempted to lower the grid resolution in order to achieve a more balanced sample distribution. Unfortunately, this adjustment did not yield satisfactory results. We anticipate that revisiting the gravity model analysis will be more fruitful once Zity has accumulated a sufficient amount of data encompassing a wider range of origin-destination pairs.

Another limitation of our study is the inability of our models to fully capture the multidimensionality of the data. We approached the temporal and spatial dimensions separately by employing the SARIMA model for temporal analysis and GWR for spatial analysis. However, we were unable to utilize models that consider both dimensions simultaneously, such as GTWR (Geographically and Temporally Weighted Regression). Additionally, we had to split the start and end event data, even though in reality, trips are connected. This disconnection of trip data introduces a limitation in capturing the full dynamics and characteristics of the mobility patterns. Future research should strive to overcome this limitation by incorporating comprehensive trip data that includes both the start and end points, enabling a more holistic understanding of travel behaviors and demand patterns.

5.2 Dealing with Multidimensional Data

The data we analyzed was spatially grouped into h3 resolution 9 grids, resulting in 1,726 hexagons. Furthermore, our temporal analysis revealed that rental event patterns varied not only between weekdays and weekends but also within different timelines throughout the day. Consequently, we had to carefully consider the applicable spatial and temporal dimensions at each step of the analysis. Managing such voluminous and complex data was challenging and running the models with the data in such scale demanded significant computational power.

Given the computational demands of the analysis, it was essential to explore various tools and platforms to identify the most efficient approaches. For instance, when conducting the geographically weighted regression (GWR) analysis, we experimented with both ArcGIS and the PySAL library in Python. Additionally, we tested different computing environments, including local instances, Google Colab, and RCF, to determine the best platform for executing our analyses. By comparing the performance of different tools and platforms, we were able to optimize our workflow and enhance the efficiency of our analysis processes.

5.3 Lack of Understanding of Milan

None of the team members had prior knowledge of Milan, which hindered the process of extracting meaningful insights from the analysis. For instance, when identifying hotspots of demands, we struggled to intuitively determine the driving factors behind the demands in each area. Fortunately, we had support from our sponsor who provided us with local insights into the city's dynamics.

6. Conclusions

This study aimed to analyze the demand patterns for free-flowing shared car service Zity in Milan and explore the driving factors behind these patterns. The findings of our analysis align with previous studies and contribute valuable insights to understanding the dynamics of mobility demand in the city.

Firstly, our analysis revealed strong temporal patterns in the mobility demand. On weekdays, the demand followed a systematic pattern, peaking during morning and evening rush hours. Conversely, on weekends, the demand exhibited a different pattern, with peak usage occurring in the middle of the day and late at night. These temporal variations highlight the importance of considering specific timeframes when planning operational activities such as charging and manual relocation.

Secondly, our correlation and Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) analyses shed light on the spatial aspects of the mobility demand. The results indicated that residential and working populations were significant driving factors behind the demands. The GWR analysis demonstrated the reasonable explanatory power of these factors in predicting demand variations across different spatial locations. By understanding the spatial patterns of demand and their association with population characteristics, optimal vehicle allocation strategies can be developed to maximize accessibility, optimize business operations, and achieve positive environmental impacts. Furthermore, our analysis revealed that riders using Zity in public transit desert zones could significantly save time compared to relying solely on public transportation. This finding further strengthens the argument that shared mobility services, such as Zity, serve as a valuable complement to public transportation, especially in areas where access to public transit options is limited or insufficient. By offering convenient and efficient mobility alternatives, shared mobility services help bridge the transportation gap and improve overall accessibility for residents in these underserved areas.

In conclusion, this study provides insights into the temporal and spatial dynamics of urban mobility demand in Milan. By considering both the temporal patterns and the spatial distribution of demand, stakeholders can make informed decisions regarding operational activities, optimize resource allocation, and enhance the accessibility and environmental sustainability of shared mobility services. Future research should focus on long-term trends

and user behavior changes to further refine and improve mobility service planning and implementation in urban areas.

7. Policy Recommendations

Based on this study, we recommend the implementation of the following policies in the city.

7.1 Establish a data sharing protocol with private entities

As our analysis shows, the data from shared mobility services holds significant value for understanding urban mobility and capturing complex patterns associated with emerging shared mobility services. On the other hand, the data needs to be handled with users' privacies in mind since the data can reveal sensitive information about individuals. The city must actively engage in maintaining the partnership with shared mobility private entities and take the lead in establishing clear guidelines for secure and responsible sharing of mobility data. These guidelines should address data privacy, security, compliance with relevant regulations, and ensure anonymization and aggregation of personal information.

7.2 Integrate shared mobility services within the framework of multi-modal routing planning

Public transit systems typically operate in areas where there is sufficient demand. However, through collaboration with the private entities like Zity, cities have the opportunity to integrate shared mobility services into their transportation networks as part of a multi-modal routing approach. It is essential for cities to encourage private entities to position themselves as collaborators rather than competitors with public transit. This approach encourages a more holistic and interconnected transportation system that caters to diverse travel needs and preferences. The partnership with the private entities will foster this integration.

7.3 Remove barriers for low-income population

It is important to acknowledge that the cost of using a private service like Zity is much higher than the public transit fare. For the low-income population to use the service freely, three key challenges can arise (Kodransky & Lewenstein, 2014).

7.4 Physical Barriers

Ensure the number of the vehicles in the low-income neighborhood.

To address the physical barrier, it is crucial to ensure an adequate number of shared mobility vehicles in low-income neighborhoods. This requires strategic placement of vehicles in these areas based on research, guaranteeing that residents have convenient access to the service.

7.5 Logistic Barriers

Make sure that private entities provide a way for using a service without a document.

The logistic barrier involves overcoming challenges related to documentation and identification requirements. Shared mobility service should provide alternative solutions for individuals who may lack the necessary documents traditionally required for accessing the service. This could include exploring options such as alternative forms of identification or implementing streamlined city-wide registration processes.

7.6 Financial Barriers

Regulate the cost for the low-income population. Incentivize the private entities with low-income specific plans. Affordability is a significant concern for low-income populations. To address the financial barrier, regulatory measures can be implemented to regulate the cost of shared mobility services for low-income individuals. Additionally, incentivizing private entities to offer low-income-specific plans or discounted rates can make the service more financially accessible to those with limited financial means.

By addressing these barriers, cities can ensure that shared mobility services are more inclusive and accessible to low-income populations. This requires a collaborative effort between public and private entities to create solutions that remove these barriers and provide equitable access to shared mobility services for all members of the community.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Credit authorship contribution statement

Hanbyul Jo: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization.

Azaria Laras: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization.

Junru Song: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization.

Zhuohao Deng: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization.

Federico Messa: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Writing – review & editing.

Giulia Ceccarelli: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Writing – review & editing.

Andrea Gorrini: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Writing – review & editing.

Rawad Choubassi: Conceptualization, Validation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing.

Thiago Soares Figueira: Conceptualization, Resources, Data curation, Writing – review & editing.

Miriam Remondini: Conceptualization, Resources, Data curation, Writing – review & editing.

All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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